

USE OF MODERN MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES OF SERVICE TO CUSTOMERS THROUGH MAIL COMMUNICATION

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Annotation: In the article, the multimedia technological processes of the postal communication tool, the essence of using advanced multimedia technologies in providing services to customers in the postal communication tool, the description of the modern multimedia services provided by the postal communication tool, the order of providing the postal communication tool services, etc. are scientifically presented by the author. analyzed, classified the factors that cause problems in the processes of providing services to customers in the mail communication tool, and also developed recommendations for further improvement of the services of the mail communication tool using modern multimedia technologies. The author based his opinions scientifically in order to eliminate various conflicts on these issues.

Key words: Mail, e-mail, electronic digital signature, e-mail, information communication technologies, multimedia, e-document, electronic payment, e-commerce, interactive services, internet network, single portal.

As a result of the consistent implementation of reforms in the field of informatization, the development of modern multimedia information and communication technologies and telecommunication systems and their widespread implementation in life, based on the tasks set for all sectors and government bodies of our republic, is achieved.

It will be possible to achieve the intended goal through the use of modern

multimedia technologies and the improvement of existing tools for the provision of postal services that meet the requirements of today. The relevance of multimedia information and communication technologies in further improving the services provided is incomparable. Currently, the Uzbekistan Post JSC and its regional branches, as well as in postal networks and communication departments, are widely implementing multimedia information and communication technologies.

Adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in recent years in order to establish a multi-sectoral information industry in our country, wide introduction of modern multimedia technologies and multimedia information and communication technologies in various sectors of the economy, as well as to provide quality services in the field of postal communication. Several decrees and decrees and government decisions indicate the importance of quality customer service in the postal service.

The decision PQ-4921 of the President of our country on December 14, 2020 on measures to fundamentally improve the system of providing postal communication services indicates that the development of postal communication is supported from the legal point of view.

Today, the postal communication system is an important sector that has its own infrastructure for the delivery of goods, banking, finance and government services, as well as letters and postal shipments at the international level and in the regions of the country.

As a result of not taking enough measures to develop the network of the National operator of Uzbekistan Post over the past periods, a number of shortcomings and problems that are expected to be solved have accumulated.

The fact that Uzbekistan Post JSC took low places in the global rating of the Postal Development Index of the Universal Postal Union indicates that there are many issues that need to be implemented in this regard.

In order to eliminate existing problems in postal communication, fundamentally improve the system of providing postal communication services, introduce modern multimedia technologies in the field, fully automate the activity of providing postal communication services, in order to include our country in the first 50 in the global ranking of postal development index the aforementioned decision was taken.

The main goal of the development of the field of postal communication tools is to fully meet the needs of customers for the transmission of various forms of information through the full use of modern multimedia technologies and the achievements of multimedia information and communication technologies, and to provide the industry with services based on new information technologies. is to turn the provider into a national operator.

We must not forget that the development of information and communication technologies affects the level of competitiveness of the country, allows to collect a large amount of information and generalize it, and opens wide opportunities for organizing management at a strategic level.

Based on world trends, in many countries, modernization of the field of postal communication is aimed at automating and mechanizing the production processes of providing postal communication services, as well as developing new types of services using information and communication technologies.

Automation based on the complex mechanization of production processes in the field of postal communication, the introduction of modern multimedia technologies into the technological processes of customer service is one of the main means of increasing labor productivity and increasing production efficiency.

Today, according to the Law adopted by the President of our country:

First of all - introduction of the final address service in cooperation with local and foreign companies engaged in the provision of postal and courier services, improvement of the traditional services of the postal communication

medium, their digitization, and information technologies for the processes of receiving, tracking and delivering shipments. and the introduction of systems was determined. Provision of modern multimedia services to the population, business and state agencies and doubling of the number of hybrid mail delivery and reception services was set.

In the second place, it was decided to create an information system of the electronic trading platform, which provides the opportunity to sell products of local manufacturers online and deliver them to customers, to establish logistics centers, and to establish and develop services that include storage and delivery of goods.

In the third place - accepting payments online through postal communication facilities, at least 1,000 post offices of the republic, doubling the types of financial services in remote areas, in particular, the acceptance of payments from residents, and the provision of banking services on the basis of outsourcing. set to capture.

Nowadays, one of the frequently raised issues in social networks is the issue of providing the population with fast, high-quality and cheap internet. Based on this, I will also give information about the activities carried out by the Ministry in this direction. In the year of development of science, enlightenment and digital economy of 2020, a number of large projects were implemented in the field of information and communication technologies.

In order to provide the population with high-quality Internet, 19 thousand kilometers of optical fiber communication lines were built to the planned objects in 2020 as part of the construction project of optical fiber communication lines. This creates ample opportunities for the use of new and modern multimedia technologies in the provision of postal services.

In this era of the development of our time, the place of the mobile communication tool is taking an increasingly deep place. It would be appropriate

to focus on providing postal communication services through mobile applications and the Internet. In particular, in 2020, 4,500 base stations were built and put into operation and 3,000 base stations were modernized in order to develop the mobile communication network. As a result, the level of coverage of the republic's settlements with mobile communication devices has reached 97%, and the level of broadband connection to the mobile Internet network has reached 87%. Taking this into account, it is necessary to implement postal communication services based on modern technologies.

In the address of the head of our country to the parliament, a number of tasks were defined for the wide introduction of the digital economy in all areas, the sustainable development of digitization in all directions. In particular, relevant agencies were instructed to develop a new version of the Laws on Postal Communication. It should be noted that effective work was done in this regard in a short period of time.

On August 23, 2007, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted Resolution No. 181 "On further improvement of cooperation of state and economic administration, local government authorities with legal entities and individuals using information and communication technologies." With this decision, the Regulation on interactive state services using multimedia information and communication technologies and the register of basic interactive state services were approved. May 4, 2011 Resolution No. 126 "On measures to introduce and use a single protected e-mail and electronic document circulation system in the executive apparatus of the Cabinet of Ministers, state and economic management, local government bodies" done. Based on the decision, electronic information exchange between the Cabinet of Ministers and state administration bodies, local government agencies is provided only through the "E-XAT" protected e-mail and the "E-document" electronic document circulation system.

One of the main shortcomings of the postal communication tool today is

that it cannot target modern multimedia technologies. Due to the rapid development of multimedia information and communication technologies on the basis of large-scale reforms carried out in our country during the years of independence, it has a significant impact on the Republic of Uzbekistan's rightful place in the global information community. Currently, information technology enters our daily work activities at lightning speed, keeping documents and ensuring their confidentiality is the main problem of every organization.

The amount of investments involved in multimedia information and communication technologies in all sectors of our republic is the proof of our opinion that the amount of net profit of state administration bodies and enterprises analyzed over the last years has increased. International experience shows that the use of multimedia information and communication technologies in public administration makes it possible to increase productivity by an average of 20% due to the reduction of time spent on interaction, processing and searching of information. During the implementation of state reforms, the economic management and government bodies are actively mastering and widely introducing information technologies.

It is known that nowadays everyone wants to do their work quickly and conveniently through a mobile communication tool. Therefore, it is necessary to organize the services in the field of postal communication in a manner worthy of this demand.

The following are the tasks that should be carried out in order to expand the activities of the postal communication tool in the electronic commerce market:

- creation of a system that enables online sales and delivery of products of local manufacturers to customers, as well as their export of goods;
- concluding contracts with entrepreneurs on placing products developed by entrepreneurs on the national online trading platform;
- introduction of a complex system in order to develop the Internet-

commerce sector;

- organization of logistics centers that allow the owners of online trading platforms to store their products, that is, to solve the problem of warehouses and to quickly pack the products purchased through the online trading platform and deliver them to customers.

It will be possible to increase the efficiency of internet commerce through postal communication by carrying out the above works.

In addition, the following should be implemented in order to provide quality service to customers based on the introduction of modern multimedia technologies.

Including:

- solving the Internet problem in postal communication facilities and providing them with modern multimedia computer equipment and mobile devices;

- introduction of an automated information system that allows receiving, sorting and online tracking of mail;

- increasing the speed of data transmission in postal communication facilities;

- to study the activities of postal operators of foreign countries and to introduce them to the post office of Uzbekistan and to implement cooperation on the exchange of shipments;

- exchange of experience and development of cooperation in the field of using new technologies with designated postal operators of foreign countries;

- organization of education and training courses for service employees on the basis of information and communication technologies;

- organization of seminars and roundtable discussions for managers and specialists of postal communication enterprises based on the study of foreign best practices in e-commerce and logistics issues;

- placing information about the products of entrepreneurs and craftsmen on

the online trading platform;

- creation of a logistics center for online stores, including storage and delivery of goods;
- establishing cooperation with local and foreign online stores;
- establishment of Mobile Communication Departments in order to bring postal communication services closer to the population.

The above-mentioned issues are necessary issues that should be implemented by means of postal communication. It is urgent to implement these issues in order to ensure the future and financial stability of the postal communication tool.

In 2020, Uzbekistan Post JSC carried out international mail exchange with more than 100 countries of the world, and the largest volume of mail exchange was between Russia, Ukraine, the USA, Germany and the United Arab Emirates [6].

Postal communication enterprises provide more than two hundred different postal communication services to consumers - residents and the national economy (long-distance and international letter sending, delivery, reception, parcels, parcels, telephone conversations, reception and delivery of telegrams giving, etc.).

In the provision of postal services, the working hours of communication media departments and the time, beginning and end of working with customers are determined by the Joint Stock Company in agreement with the authorities. A mailbox is placed for the convenience of residents, so that they can send ordinary letters and postcards from the city, railway, airport and other settlements at any time. Each mailbox shows its number, how many times a day correspondence is received, and what day it is not received. In this regard, it is advisable to act according to the customer's demand.

The automated system is created on the basis of a thin client system with centralized database management and software management capabilities based on

WEB technology. The international electronic money transfers of the Universal Postal Union of the automated system are connected to the "IFS light" system, which opens the door of great opportunities to the postal communication tool.

Using this system, it is possible to make local and international money transfers. This creates a basis for increasing the efficiency of the money transfer service and providing services based on new modern multimedia information technologies.

With the launch of the electronic money transfer system, the technological process of postal money transfers has been fully automated. In this case, the process from the time of receiving the money transfer from the client to the payment is automated. In order to increase competitiveness in the postal service market, a program for the implementation of an automated information system of electronic money transfers was developed, and now it is necessary to improve this program based on the introduction of information and communication technologies and new technologies.

The Ministry of Development of Information Technologies and Communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan implements bilateral cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of information technologies and communications with other countries and international organizations in the field.

By becoming a member of the Universal Postal Union, the Republic of Uzbekistan gained the following opportunities:

Using the World Postal Convention and additional agreements, establishing uniform international postal communication tools and participating in international postal exchanges;

Organization of postal cooperation with the Union member states.

In order to perform these tasks in a high-quality way, what is necessary for the postal communication tool is to adapt to the requirements of this time and integrate with advanced technologies.

Bilateral cooperation with foreign countries. Currently, the Ministry of Information Technology and Communications Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan cooperates with the Republic of Korea, the People's Republic of China, Japan, India, Singapore, Malaysia, Germany, Switzerland, the USA and many other countries that are achieving advanced results in the field. established strong communication tools. Within the framework of regional cooperation in the field of communications established between CIS member countries, effective cooperation in the field has been established.

The basis of international cooperation is the establishment of international agreements, agreements and legal documents in the field of communications, information and telecommunications. Technically, the development of enterprises directly depends on the improvement of their management methods. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account not only the solvency of the population in one or another region, but also social traditions and specific features of the living environment.

The use of foreign experience in introducing new services in the field of postal communications, following the path taken by developed countries is one of the most effective directions for the development of the field of communications.

Let's take the Russian post as an example. The post of Russia is considered a comprehensive and highly developed industry and provides services to all segments of the population. Russian Post has implemented the online system of pochtamarket, which provides customers with a number of services.

Russian Post has introduced a system of online subscription to newspapers and magazines, which allows customers to subscribe to or order newspapers and magazines from their homes or workplaces.

Implementation of the services of Russian Post such as Pochtamarket service and online subscription in Uzbekistan Post JSC will lead to an increase in the number of customers of the postal communication service and an increase in

the scope of income.

The introduction of new types of customer service on the basis of information communication technologies provides the future perspective of the postal communication industry.

The Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the body responsible for forming and maintaining the Unified Register of operators and providers of postal communication tools. Therefore, the fate and future activity of the postal communication tool is in the hands of this ministry.

The single register is maintained electronically in the online mode, the business entities that carry out the sending and delivery of mail and courier shipments have the status of the operator or provider of the postal communication tool in the established order from the day of their entry into the Single Register. .

Benefits established by law on customs fees for goods entering the Republic of Uzbekistan through international mail and courier shipments are applied only to operators and providers included in the Unified Register.

The costs of the creation and implementation of the information system of the Unified Register of operators and providers of postal communications are financed from the funds of the Fund for the Development of Information and Communication Technologies.

According to the regulation on the procedure for forming and maintaining the Unified Register of operators and providers of postal communication, the main tasks and directions of maintaining the Unified Register of operators and providers of postal communication are as follows:

creation of a single electronic data bank on operators and providers of postal communication tools providing postal and courier services;

Formation of a database on the state and potential of the market of postal communication services in the Republic of Uzbekistan;

to determine the priorities for the effective development of the market of postal communication services, as well as to evaluate the state of the current legislation and develop proposals for improvement;

conducting systematic monitoring to ensure compliance with regulatory legal documents and postal security requirements in the field;

development of postal communication services and assistance in providing high-quality and competitive services.

The introduction of new types of customer service on the basis of information communication technologies provides the future perspective of the postal communication industry.

It is desirable to improve the postal service using the experiences of the Italian Post (Poste Italiane), which is considered the leader in terms of the reputation of the postal service and the level of customer service among European countries.

The Poste Italiane group of companies combines four business lines: Postal Services, Postal Bank, Express Delivery and Courier Services.

In addition, I believe that along with the development of information and communication technologies in the field of postal services, it is necessary to pay serious attention to issues such as increasing the capacity of personnel. Because no matter how advanced technology is the enterprise, if the workers cannot use the existing technologies enough, the created opportunities will not give their results.

Comprehensive plans should be developed to implement this issue. For example, training courses should be opened in regional branches of JSC "Uzbekistan Post" in order to improve the qualifications of employees, and training of employees should be carried out based on the schedule. The issue of improving skills is also of urgent importance.

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